

THE IMPORTANCE OF BEGALI KASIMOV'S WORKS IN COVERING THE
PROBLEM OF EDUCATIONAL REFORM IN THE MEDIA

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Abstract. The article analyzes the personal concept of Professor, Doctor of Philological Sciences Begali Kasimov, as well as the scientist's articles, such as fidelity to the truth, impartial analysis of the problems of Uzbek literature during the period of national Renaissance, preparation of high-quality textbooks, expressed higher and comprehensive schools, presentation of Uzbek science to the world.

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The study of social problems is the main criterion of philosophy, aesthetics, art and literature from social fields. Mass media and all their genres can be included in these social spheres. Since mass media focus on the development of society and positive solutions to human problems, this is a natural process that covers almost all spheres.

The development of a country is determined by its youth, the potential of tomorrow's mature personnel. This can be achieved by modernizing education, setting the right personnel policy, updating the content of taught subjects, enriching them with elements of modern methods, focusing on interdisciplinary integration.

Every person who feels love for the nation, a sense of belonging to the Motherland, has an instinct to care about its future. The personal concept of Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor Begali Kasimov also entered the field with the aim of being faithful to the truth, impartially analyzing the problems of Uzbek literature during the period of national revival, preparing high-quality textbooks for higher and comprehensive schools and presenting Uzbek science to the world.

The issue of education reform is a complex process that cannot be postponed, and if it is ignored, decades will be lost. A number of journalistic articles by the scientist have been published in the media, concerning the introduction of innovations into the education system, the organization of modern trends and specializations. In addition to textbooks for grades 5, 7, 9 and 10, he also prepared a textbook on national literature of the Renaissance for higher education institutions with 30 printing plates. He was extremely serious in all matters, incomparably devoted to his profession.

Literary scholar Kazakboy Yoldoshev in his article "Kongil Yolcini" describes the scholar as follows: "Brother Begali was a distinguished scholar of the Turkic world, a man and an expert who raised the honor and reputation of the Uzbeks. That is why he was sometimes invited to Kazakhstan, sometimes to Turkey, sometimes to Tatarstan, and they listened to what he said. He was a scholar who thought on a global scale. That is why he believed that science should not be confined to its nest. I directly observed and witnessed at a number of conferences and personal conversations that the scholar knows Turkish literature better than Turkish scholars, the history

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and literature of Crimea than Crimean specialists, and the history of Tatar literature better than the Tatars" [1].

In the 3rd issue of the journal "Language and Literary Education" for 1998, an important article by the scholar was published, devoted to educational policy, under the title "Current issues of teaching the history of Uzbek literature in higher education". The article is notable for its richness in reasoning, developed proposals, as well as the need to carry out urgent reforms in the field of education. The article is remarkable for its richness in reasoning, developed proposals, and the need for urgent reforms in the field of education. In the introduction to the article, the scientist regretfully notes that rare examples of rich Uzbek literature were scattered across different regions as a result of unprecedented disasters that befell the people, or rather, they were taken away. Thus, it is clearly written that from our most ancient written manuscripts to several copies of newspapers, magazines and printed books of the early 20th century, they spread to Europe, Eurasia and India. In particular, he emphasizes that beautiful, unique and rare examples of magnificent Uzbek literature are in museums in France, England, Austria, Russia, Turkey, Iran, India. In particular, he regrets that we do not have the original works of Alisher Navoi, even his autograph. "Tatar orientalists in Finland report that in a number of their libraries there are countless Uzbek books and examples of the press relating to the history and literature of Turkestan, dating back to the times of Tsarist Russia and not yet recorded anywhere" [2]. It seems that in the process of preparing this article, the scientist is trying to indicate the exact geographical location of the sources of Uzbek literature. He hopes that such information will be passed on to researchers who, by the will of fate, end up in distant Finland. The scientist's inner desire is to find, read, transform and convey these sources to the public. Another reason for providing this information is the recognition of the growing interest in oriental studies, including Uzbek studies, in world education. He is especially proud of the creation of Turkology centers, Uzbek language and literature departments in some European universities in recent years. At a time when citizens of distant countries are looking for the roots of human history and civilization, they encourage science from all over the world. Specialists in the Uzbek language and literature work in Germany, the United States of America, and the foreign country of Japan. In addition, in the article devoted to this educational system, the scientist reports that there is a need to get acquainted and exchange experiences with scientists directly conducting research on the Uzbek language and literature in other higher education systems of the world, in research centers. At this point in the article, another interesting piece of information is provided: "In 1993, Edward Allworth contacted the Translation Center of Uzbekistan and sent the addresses of 33 well-known bookstores located in different cities of the world, and told them that they would buy any book related to Uzbek literature." If there is very clear information for visualization, secondly, in the introduction to the article there is also a reasonable idea of the study of Uzbek literature on a global scale. The fact that the scientist tries to explain each sentence, idea, show its root is a reflection in his personality of the concept of responsibility, respect for work and devotion to science.

He was glad that in the first 10 years of independence, the issue of creating textbooks for higher education was still relevant. To achieve this goal, he also proposed that the curriculum and scientific programs be discussed by relevant experts, and testing measures be developed.

The scientist's concern is more clearly seen in the opinion that each area should work together, not separately. The homogeneity of the educational system, especially in the teaching of Uzbek literature, which has been preserved for many years, that it has not gone beyond the

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expertise based on "socialist realism" in the analysis of works of art, currently requires the development of various methods of Western literary criticism and their use in our country from the point of view of nationalism. It is also said here that the teachers-methodologists, general education teachers bear a great responsibility, updating knowledge, applying new methodological methods.

Although the eighth year of independence is still ongoing, he criticized the lack of articles on the methods of teaching Uzbek literature and the principles of studying works related to the history of our literature. This criticism is justified, because methodological support is needed for teachers working in remote regions and regions. The approach to the artistic text, the values expressed in it, Islamic philosophy, national spirit, scientific articles that correctly guide the analysis and interpretation of patriotic feelings can also perform the function of the "Teacher's Book" in a certain sense even temporarily. Considering the reform of the literary education system an urgent task, the scientist also made proposals that could well become the subject of new scientific works. "From the point of view of periodization of the history of our centuries-old literature, determining its stages, determining development trends, today there are no works written on the content and essence of our independence. The concept of teaching Uzbek literature in universities has not been created" [2]. This article, written almost twenty-four years ago, gives the impression of foreseeing today's reforms. That is, academic independence is provided in creating curricula and scientific programs in accordance with a specific concept of a higher education institution, put forward by a scientist a quarter of a century ago. The most important thing is that the teacher's thoughts fully correspond to today's speech. "It is probably better that there is no single program on Uzbek literature in universities. Because, in the end, each higher education institution should have its own image" [2]. The above ideas can be applied not only to literary education, but to all areas of education. It would not be an exaggeration to say that the answer to such bright thoughts and dreams are the current reforms of pedagogical universities.

The scientist said that he should have full knowledge of the work of Alisher Navoi, teach and interpret ghazals at the Higher Education Institution, which prepares a pure philologist and specialist in Uzbek language and literature. One of them is the issue of literature and its place in society. It is known that there is a difference in the approach of the West and the East to the terminological interpretation of literature. The Eastern approach interprets literature in connection with morals. This revolution was made by our ancestors at the beginning of the 20th century. Indeed, if we take the literature of the next one and a half thousand years, almost all works are connected with one main issue - man and his morals. The dominance of this idea did not deny high artistry [2].

Also, B.Kasimov's views on the system of education, teaching, studying and covering Uzbek literature were continued in many articles, speeches and lectures. For example, his views on the art of poetry, which must be studied, the methodology that forms the ability to find examples of works of art, the technique of working with classical texts, the need to know the old Uzbek script, knowledge of analysis methods deserve attention.

Begali Kasimov paid attention not only to the problems of historical research, but also to almost all issues of literary education. For example, the field of literary criticism in the years of independence emphasizes that it should develop in a new way. In the criticism of the post-Soviet period, only those works prevailed in which the motives of serving the government and the party, the leadership of the figure of the "great master", the glorification of the working man prevailed.

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Non-compliance with the above criteria was subjected to harsh criticism, as a result of which, as can be seen in the example of the work of Abdulla Kahhor, versions of large canvas works, such as "Sarob", were first censored, and in addition, versions with auto-censorship appeared. B.Kasimov, speaking about the problem of literary criticism, emphasizes that its task is not to judge, but to sort. He supported his opinion with quotes from the article by Mahmudhodja Behbudi "Criticism sorts".

With his scientific views, he proved that in a work of art, the idea and content must be harmonious, otherwise the artistic standard will be violated. In particular, classical sources emphasized that the theme of love in the works of Alisher Navoi should be considered not only from a secular point of view, but also from a theological-mystical one, but this is not a strict measure. He gently criticized the fact that the views in subsequent studies remain one-sided, and considered it acceptable to express his own views: "In addition, one should not look for only divine content in Navoi's interpretation of love, as we have done so far. They mainly look for secular content. However, in some articles and brochures, there is a tendency towards this. In this, one should proceed from Navoi's own views on metaphorical love and true love. The border between these two concepts, both in his views and in his work, are, in our opinion, not mutually exclusive, but rather complementary phenomena. "Their boundaries are sometimes imperceptible" – a tone of impartiality prevails in his thoughts.

In addition, he assessed the introduction of new sciences, the development of their programs and textbooks as a product of historical conditions. "In particular, it was possible to study modern Uzbek literature, which was formed at the end of the last century and gave its first fruits at the beginning of the 20th century, and in the 20s, despite the strong pressure of time, it became a full-fledged literature" - he boldly wrote his thoughts that he could not express for years. The introduction of the term "Uzbek literature of national revival" into science and the creation of a scientific school on this basis are closely associated with the name of Professor Begali Kasimov. "According to our ancestors, language and literature are the immortal soul of the nation, the mirror of its life, a teacher-educator. It passes on to generations the way of life of its ancestors, moral philosophy, all the good and bad sides, educates generations in the spirit of the traditions of the nation, connects the centuries. From Behbudi to Fitrat and Cholpon, from Avlani to Hamza and Kadiri, the purpose and content of literature were interpreted in this way, and this approach became fixed and a priority" [2]. Therefore, the scientist emphasized that through this idea, modern literature is an important bridge between the past and present development, and its services in conveying the unique heritage of ancestors to generations in new ways and forms.

In other articles and interviews, the scientist outlined such priority tasks as teaching Uzbek literature of the period of national revival, literary studies in general, development of the education system, intensive continuation of the issue of training mature personnel. In his speeches in the press, he also gave proposals and recommendations on periodization, methods of teaching literature.

Another article entitled "The education of the generation is the education of the nation" was published in the newspaper "Fidokor" on June 14, 2001, "National University: high status, bright prospects" in the issue of the newspaper "Literature and Art of Uzbekistan" on February 1, 2000, in the October 10, 2002 issue of this newspaper, "Literature and its periodization", "To wake up is to live in harmony with the world", "The role of national literature in educating the growing generation in the spirit of national patriotism", "National program of personnel training:

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international cooperation in the field of personnel training with education" (speech at the scientific council of the National University of Uzbekistan, July 2, 1998 - emphasis is ours - Sh.Kasimov), the issue of national ideology and personality education", "Language is the honor of the nation", "Creation of new textbooks should become a state policy" (People's Word, 1992, June 12), "Creation of new textbooks" (People's Word, 1992, December 12), various aspects of the education system studied from the angles of journalistic and literary studies.

The scientist himself worked tirelessly to fill the gaps in textbooks, with the ideas he proposed in his articles. He prepared and published textbooks, teaching aids, and methodological guidelines for students and teachers of higher and comprehensive schools. The following table provides information on the teaching aids created by the scientist:

Table 1

Textbooks and teaching aids prepared by Begali Kasymov for higher and comprehensive schools

№	Name	Publisher, type and year of publication	HEI	Comprehensive school
1	Course work. Uzbek literature	ToshSU publishing house, methodological manual. 1985. 3.0 p.p.	For students of the Uzbek philology faculty of universities of the 3rd year	
2	Life and creative activity of Ghulam Karimov	T.: 1989, co-author	bibliographic guide for philological students.	
3	Navoi Khan	T.: Teacher, 1993. 20.0 p.p.	Methodical guide	
4	Uzbek literature	T.: Teacher, 1993. 20.0 p.p.		Complex for class 10
5	Abdulla Avloni	History of Uzbek pedagogy. T.: Teacher, 1997, 0.2 p.p.	Guide to HEI	
6	Uzbek literature	Teacher, 1999. 25.0 p.p.		Complex for class 10
7	Literature	T.: Writer, 2001, 20.16 p.p. (co-author).		Textbook-complex for 7th grade
8	Uzbek literature	T.: Literature and Art, 2001, (co-author).		Textbook for grade 10, 3rd edition
9	Uzbek literature	T.: Literature and Art, 2000. 23.7 p.p. (co-author); 3rd		Textbook for 10th grade

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		edition, T.: Literature and Art, 2001.		
10	Literature	T.: Teacher, 2000. 20.16 p.p. (co-author), 2nd ed.		Textbook for 7th grade
11	Literature	T.: Spirituality, 2002, 18.0 p.p. (co-author).		Textbook for 9th grade
12	Teacher's book	T.: Spirituality, 2002, 12.0 p.p. (co-author).		9th grade textbook set, methodology

The table shows that the scientist, along with his scientific work, wrote a number of textbooks and contributed to the development of national education.

Being both a scientist and a publicist with a sharp pen, he studied the lessons of the past in his articles, simply and fluently explained the ideology of national independence, and educated the younger generation with high spirituality and personal values. He reflected his thoughts about the education system in a combination of emotional and logical thinking.

In the work of a scientist, the concept of Man is always formed on the basis of truth, selflessness, spiritual and moral criteria. That is why we see that these three things played a big role in his words, articles and activities. When approaching issues of the education system and literature, the personality of an individual intellectual, his social status, devotion to duties and tasks are clearly manifested. In essence, these are the dreams and ideals of a phenomenon responsible for the development of society.

How we have witnessed the renewal of the media and public thinking: the role of the Uzbek national literature of the Renaissance in this matter is largely facilitated by periodical journalism, scientific and literary environment, conferences devoted to the interpretation of social phenomena.

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5. Yangi darsliklar yaratish // Xalq so'zi, 1992, 12-dekabr. 0,1 b.t.